

Analysis of Academic Ties: A Case Study of Mathematics Genealogy

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Abstract: Analyzing social networks of communities helps us obtain local and large-scale information about the social relations. We can observe how structural as well as behavioral changes occur among the members of a social network over years. In this paper, we analyze academic ties of mathematicians using the *Mathematics Genealogy Project* data. Additionally, using university and nation information of mathematicians, we examine which universities or nations are more correlated as well as how these correlations change over the years.

Keywords - Academic ties, mathematics genealogy, social network.

1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of social network analysis is to investigate the relationships in different communities which can be as diverse as the social structure of communication over the Internet [1], transportation network [2], network of rivers [3] and food webs [4]. Knowledge of the structure of a network enables us to gain insight into how rapidly information may spread through the network, the resilience of it to attacks, and the social role of individual entities in forming it. Network of academic ties can be examined to understand how researchers correlate with each other as well as their preferences of universities and nations to study and work at.

In this paper, we examine different aspects of the academic network. First, we explore structural characteristics of the advisor-advisee relations among mathematicians. Then, we analyze the academic relations among the universities and the countries by deriving the Ph.D. institutions of professors. To perform these analyses, we gather data from *The Mathematics Genealogy Project* site, which collects information of mathematicians starting from 1600s [5]. Even though this database has been studied extensively, to best of our knowledge, the advisor-advisee relation has not been analyzed using the social network theories.

The genealogy project provides a database of researcher's name, graduation year, graduated university, and country of the university. We crawled the website to gather the information about 148,866 researchers at the time of our study. The data provided by the website is incomplete as it does not include all doctoral degrees. We also filtered various distortions observed in the raw data to the extent possible.

In the rest of paper, we first describe the overall network formation process in Section 2. In Section 3, we analyze different aspects of networks. In Section 4, we analyze the relationship between number of researchers and development of a country by considering World Wars. In Section 5, we conclude the paper with key insights from our analyses.

2. NETWORK FORMATION

Using advisor information of researchers, we constructed an advisor-advisee network. By nature, this network mostly exhibits tree property as a sample advisor-advisee relationship is illustrated in Figure 1. The structural characteristics of this network inform us how researchers are connected. As detailed in Section 3.2, we can also extract interesting relationships between advisor and advisees considering local structures.

Figure 1: General structure of academic network

We constructed the university networks by extracting the university information of a researcher and his/her students. For example, if a researcher obtains his/her dissertation from the *University of Texas at Dallas* and later graduates doctoral students from the *University of Nevada, Reno*, then we insert a link between the *University of Texas at Dallas* and the *University of Nevada, Reno*. This relation is not a direct relation between universities, as it occurs when a researcher graduates from a university and works at another university. Analyzing this network gives insight into which universities exchange researchers as well as which universities are more central to the growth of academic world.

The country network is derived by using a similar approach. For instance, if a researcher graduates from a university located in the *United States* and graduates students from a university located in *Turkey*, then we add a link between the *United States* and *Turkey* in the country network. This network gives information about which countries exchange more researchers as well as which countries are more central in the academic community.

3. NETWORK ANALYSIS

In this section, we analyze the constructed networks using social network metrics and provide an analysis of the results.

3.1. Number of Mathematicians

To observe transformations of university and country networks, we divided them into 10 year periods. We chose a decade because it provides sufficient time period to realize changes. Although Math Genealogy project lists researchers starting from 1500s, the number of researchers is very small to be considered as a complex network until 1900s. Hence, we discarded

them (in total 1,653) when we examine evolution of university and country networks.

Figure 2 presents the number of researchers over the decades in log-scale. We can observe that after 1960s there is a great increase in the number of mathematicians. Even though the data is not complete, it reveals general trends such as which decades are breakpoints for the academic growth.

Figure2: Number of mathematicians over decades (log-scale)

3.2 Structural Behavior of Advisor-Advisee Network

General structure of the advisor-advisee network is shown in Figure 1. However, the network is not always tree structured as there are cases that introduces circles. In particular, co-advising of a student inserts a node with more than one parent.

To identify possible network structures, we used FanMod tool [6] that finds ratios of common sub-graphs where size of the sub-structure ranges from 3 to 8 nodes. In our network, we searched for sub-graphs of 3, 4 and 5 nodes as the larger subgraphs were not revealing interesting cases.

Figure 3 displays all sub-graphs of 3 nodes and their ratio of occurrences. As we expected, most of the 3-node sub-structures are in the form of one parent and two children as shown in Figure3-(a). Math Genealogy project has limited information of researchers who lived before 1500s. The maximum depth we observed from a researcher to his academic descendants is 18. This is also reflected with the occurrence of Figure 3-(b). Moreover, we see that co-advising is observed in 1.8% of sub-graphs. Although with low frequency, an advisor and a student may co-advise another student as shown in Figure 3-(d).

Figure 3: Basic 3 node sub-structures.

Similarly, Figure 4 presents the most frequent sub-graphs of 4 and 5 node structures in the advisor-advisee network. For all 3, 4 and 5 node structures, a single advisor with multiple students is dominant. Even it is a dominant structure, its frequency decreases as the number of nodes increase (which is discussed in Section 3.3).

Figure 4: Most observed 4 and 5 node sub-structures.

Figure 5 presents interesting cases of advisor-advisee relations even though the occurrence is very small. In Figure 5-(a), two advisees are co-advised by advisors where there is also an advisor-advisee relation among the advisors. Figure 5-(b) presents two students of an advisor who co-advise a student. Figure 5-(c) corresponds to researchers who co-advise 3 different students.

Figure 5: Some interesting 4 and 5 node structures.

3.3 Number of Advisees

In the advisor-advisee network, 70% of researchers are leaf nodes that indicate they have no recorded graduated students. Moreover, 41% of non-leaf nodes have 1 child, i.e., a single graduated student.

Figure 6 indicates the number of researchers with a given number of students and the cumulative distribution (CDF) of researchers with respect to the number of students. In the CDF, only researchers with at least a student are considered. Interestingly, we observed researchers with more than 100 graduated students.

Figure 6: Total number and the Cumulative Distribution Function of researchers with a given number of students (considering non-zeros).

3.4 Characteristics of University and Country Networks

In this part, we examine the characteristics of the university and the country networks. Then, to observe how the academic network evolved over the years, we examined network metrics for individual decades starting from 1900.

Figure 8: Academic ties of universities where node size indicates centrality.

Figure 7: Academic ties of countries. Node size is relative to centrality.

Figure 7 presents the academic ties of 104 countries in the database. In this network average node degree is 17.8. Assortativity coefficient of the network is 0.005 indicating a non-assortative behavior. That is, countries are not more or less likely to exchange researchers based on the degree of the other country. Clustering coefficient of the network is 0.37. The clustering is much higher than expected value for a random network of same size, i.e., 0.006, which is observed in the small-world networks.

Similarly, Figure 8 displays the academic ties of 1860 universities in the data set. Average degree of a university is 19.6. The assortativity coefficient of the network is 0.05 which also indicates non-assortativity of universities in exchanging researchers. Clustering coefficient of the network is 0.23 while a random network with the same size is 0.05. Similar to country network, this indicates that the university network exhibits the small-world characteristics. Moreover, the observed top clique size is 6 indicating that these universities have exchanged researchers with others.

Figure 9 and Figure 10 presents the degree distribution of university and country networks, respectively. In the university network, we observe a power law degree distribution with a fat tail. This indicates that few universities have exchanged very large number of researchers with other universities while many universities have exchanged researchers with a few. On the other hand, the degree distribution of the country network is not a clear cut power-law as of the university network. We believe this is due to the limited number of countries, i.e., 104.

Figure 9: Degree distribution of the university network

Figure 10: Degree distribution of the country network

3.5 Evolution of Networks over the Decades

Figure 11 shows the density of university network over the decades when we only consider the exchanges during the decade. As seen in the figure, density continuously decreases over the decades. This is contrary to traditional social networks where we observe the densification of the network as time passes. In this case, we think the decrease is caused by the increasing number of universities which is not supported by enough number of researchers.

Figure 11: Density of university network over the decades

Figure 12 presents the average degree of university network over the decades where we observe a generally increasing trend. While network density decreased, the average degree exhibits an increase over the time. This is because of the fact that the degree is linearly correlated to the number of nodes whereas in the case of the density it is quadratic.

Figure 12: Average degree of university network over the decades

Figure 13 shows the density of the country network over the decades. Even though the density is much higher, it does not exhibit a clear trend as the university network.

Figure 13: Density of country network over the decades

Figure 14 presents the average degree of the country network over the years. Similar to the university network, we observe an increase in the average degree. This implies an increase of researcher exchange between universities from different countries.

Figure 14: Average degree of country network over the decades

3.6 Co-Advising of Researchers

Co-advising indicates the collaboration among researchers when advising students. Figure 15 presents the frequency of co-advising over all advisor-advisee relations for different decades. There is no clear trend in the figure.

Figure 15: Co-advising ratio changes over the decades

4. WORLD WARS & ACADEMIC NETWORK

In this section, we inspect the correlation between World Wars and the academic world. For this, we looked at the 1st and 2nd world wars to see researcher exchanges of countries that had big impacts.

Table 1 shows 5 nations with the highest normalized degrees during 1910-1920. As observed in the table, Germany has considerably higher degree centrality by having most researcher exchanges with the other countries. Austria was also another impactful country during the decade. Although we cannot directly relate this table to power of a country, it presents development of a country in terms of academic ties.

Table 1 : Top 5 Nations with the highest degrees during 1910-1920

Nation	Normalized Degree Value
Germany	0.050
Austria	0.038
Switzerland	0.029
Poland	0.024
Netherlands	0.024

In the 2nd world war, Germany was the country that initiated the war and the United States was the country that ended the war. In Table 2, we can see these two countries having the highest academic relations.

Table 2 : Top 5 Countries with the highest degrees during 1935-1945

Nation	Normalized Degree
United States	0.100
Germany	0.067
Austria	0.430
United Kingdom	0.043
Poland	0.038

United States gained considerable power between 1st and 2nd World War which is also reflected in its educational impact in Figure 16. Additionally, after Germany lost 2nd World War, there is a considerable decrease in its academic relations as seen in Figure 17.

Figure 16: Number of researchers graduated from universities in the United States.

Figure 17: Number of researchers graduated from universities in Germany.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we analyzed academic networks formed by advisor-advisee relation. Although there are rare cases, the network is mostly composed of tree structures. By analyzing this network, we observed that co-advising among researchers fluctuates from 10% to 20% over the decades. Moreover, 80% of all researchers who received Ph.D. degree have no listed student.

We also constructed university and country networks based on the transfer of researchers from one university to another one. Both the university and the country networks have low density and low average degree which implies weak relations among universities in terms of hiring researchers. Both networks are non-assortative which means there is no explicit tendency toward popular or non-popular ones in forming ties. Finally, we analyzed degree characteristic of university network and observed that, countries that have considerable impact on world wars have high academic relations during the world war periods.

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